

RUBEANIC ACID AND ITS DERIVATIVES AS COLORIMETRIC REAGENTS PART II. DIMETHYL- AND DIETHYL- RUBEANIC ACIDS

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NN'-Dimethyl- and -diethyl-rubeanic acids react in a similar manner as rubeanic acid, furnishing coloured precipitates with solutions of salts of various metals like, Pd, Au, Ag, etc. The solubilities of these metal complexes also closely follow those of rubeanates. Spot tests of Cu, Co, Ni and Pd show identification limits comparable to those of the parent compound. Spectrophotometric determinations of the above metals, excluding copper, have also been made as in the case of rubeanic acid.

The use of rubeanic acid in the spectrophotometric determination of cobalt, nickel, palladium, silver and ruthenium has been reported earlier (this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 432). The introduction of certain radicals into organic reagents, containing certain reactive groups, has been found to exert an influence on the solubility of the reagent, on its ability to form salts and on the solubility characteristics of its reaction products. The influence of weighting and/or size effect is considered to be mainly responsible for such a behaviour. A comparative study of certain disubstituted rubeanic acids was therefore deemed desirable with a view to examining the influence of substitution on their properties as analytical reagents (Xavier and Rây, *Science & Culture*, 1954, 21, 694).

EXPERIMENTAL

The *NN'*- dialkyl substituted rubeanic acids were obtained by warming rubeanic acid with the corresponding primary amines in alcohol (Wallach and Reinhardt, *Annalen*, 1891, 262, 354; Woodburn and Sroog, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1952, 17, 376).

Dimethyl rubeanic acid ($\text{CH}_3\text{-NH-CS-CS-NH-CH}_3$) and diethylrubeanic acid ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{-NH-CS-CS-NH-C}_2\text{H}_5$) behave in a manner almost similar to rubeanic acid (Feigl and Badian, unpublished work; cf. Feigl, "Chemistry of Specific, Selective and Sensitive Reactions", p. 44, Academic Press, New York, 1949). Like rubeanic acid they give coloured precipitates with solutions of salts of various metals like copper, cobalt, nickel, palladium, silver, gold, platinum, lead, mercury, etc. The characteristic properties of these precipitates are summarised in Table I.

TABLE I

Metals.	(I) Dimethylrubeanic acid.	(II) Diethylrubeanic acid.
Copper	Deep green ppt. with a faint blue tinge from ammoniacal, neutral or weakly acid (acetic) solns. Almost insoluble in dil. acids, alkalies and in all the common solvents.	Green ppt. with a blue tinge. Same as I.
Cobalt	Deep brown ppt. in ammoniacal medium. Insoluble in dil. acids and alkalies. Fairly soluble in pyridine (orange-yellow soln.), extractable by <i>isoamyl</i> or <i>isobutyl</i> alcohol, ethyl or amyl acetate and chloroform).	Same as I. The pyridine soln. is extractable also by benzene and toluene.
Nickel	Reddish violet ppt. in ammoniacal medium. Insoluble in dil. acids or alkalies. Easily soluble in pyridine (reddish pink solution extractable by common solvents).	Deep purple-red ppt. in ammoniacal medium. Solubility same as I. The pyridine soln. is pink-red.
Palladium	Orange-yellow ppt. in very dil. acid medium. Slightly soluble in dil. acids and decomposed by dil. alkalies. Soluble in most of the solvents. Pyridine soln. is coloured orange-yellow.	Same as I.
Silver	Orange-yellow ppt. from neutral soln. decomposed by dil. acids or alkalies.	Deep orange-yellow ppt. in neutral soln., same as I.
Gold	Yellowish white ppt. from dil. acid soln., decomposed on standing.	Orange-yellow ppt., same as I.
Platinum	Fale yellow ppt. from acid soln., turning orange-yellow on standing.	Orange-brown ppt.
Lead	Voluminous yellow ppt. from neutral or alkaline soln., decomposed by dil. acids.	Yellow ppt., behaves as I.
Mercury (II)	White ppt. from neutral soln., stable towards dil. ammonia or alkali solns., decomposed by dil. acids.	Same as I.

Manganese, chromium, titanium, tin, molybdenum, tungsten, vanadium, zinc, cadmium, uranium, arsenic, antimony, etc. do not react with these reagents. Ruthenium gives a coloured solution (blue) in acid medium as with rubeanic acid.

Spot Test Detections.—Cu, Co, Ni and Pd can be detected by the spot-tests. The following procedure was adopted. A drop of the sample solution was placed in the depression of the spot plate, followed by another drop of very dilute ammonia. One drop of the reagent solution (0.1% alcoholic) was placed very near to the first drop. As the drops mixed together, characteristic colours or precipitates were observed on the boundary zone. Copper is identified by its light green precipitate, cobalt by yellowish brown colour or precipitate and nickel by pink colour or precipitate. Palladium is detected by the yellow colour, produced in a similar way, but without adding ammonia solution. The formation of characteristic colours took about 3 to 5 minutes after the drops got mixed. For comparison, a blank was also carried out. The following identification and concen-

tration limits were obtained: Cu, 0.18 γ ($1:2.3 \times 10^5$); Ni, 0.04 γ ($1:1.25 \times 10^6$); Co, 0.025 γ ($1:2 \times 10^6$); Pd, 0.067 γ ($1:5 \times 10^5$).

Spectrophotometric Determinations.—Co, Ni and Pd have been spectrophotometrically determined in aqueous pyridine solution, using alcoholic-sodium hydroxide solutions of dimethyl- and diethylrubeanic acids. Copper, however, could not be determined in this way due to the low solubility of the copper rubeanate in pyridine solution. The determination of ruthenium was carried out in strong hydrochloric acid solution, using an alcoholic solution of the reagent. The sensitivities of the cobalt and palladium reactions are almost the same as those with rubeanic acid, while nickel and ruthenium estimations give slightly higher values. The colour development was retarded by excess of alkali, when the diethyl derivative was employed for the determinations.

Determination of Cobalt

Cobalt developed an orange-yellow colour in aqueous pyridine with an alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution of diethyl- or dimethyl- rubeanic acid. The colour development was rapid in presence of sodium acetate, although for higher concentrations of cobalt (>3 p.p.m.) 30 to 45 minutes were required to reach the maximum intensity. The optical density thereafter remained unaltered for more than 24 hours at the room temperature. A Unicam SP 600 spectrophotometer was used for the measurement.

FIG. 1
Absorption curves.

- Curve I — 1 p.p.m. Co; 5 c.c. pyridine; 1 c.c. dimethylrubeanic acid reagent soln. and 1 c.c. sodium acetate soln. in 25 c.c. final volume.
 Curve II — Same as for I; 1 c.c. diethylrubeanic acid reagent soln.
 Curve III — 2 p.p.m. Ni; 5 c.c. pyridine; 2 c.c. dimethylrubeanic acid reagent soln. in final volume 25 c.c.
 Curve IV — Same as III; 1 c.c. diethylrubeanic acid reagent soln.
 Curve V — 2 p.p.m. Pd; 5 c.c. pyridine; 1 c.c. dimethylrubeanic acid reagent soln. in final volume 25 c.c.
 Curve VI — Same as for V; 1 c.c. diethylrubeanic acid reagent soln.
 Curve VII — 2 p.p.m. Ru; 1 c.c. of reagent (dimethyl or diethylrubeanic acid) soln. in final volume 25 c.c.

Standard cobalt solution contained 17 Co/c.c. Reagent solution was prepared by mixing equal volumes of 0.1% alcoholic solution of dimethyl- or diethyl-rubeanic acid and $N/4$ aqueous NaOH solution. In presence of NaOH, dimethyl- or diethyl-rubeanic acid solution was coloured faintly yellow. 1% Aqueous sodium acetate was used.

Absorption Curves.—Against a reagent blank, the orange-yellow colour of the test solution gave constant absorption in the region 385-395 $m\mu$ (cf. Curves I & II, Fig. 1). Measurements of optical density were made at 395 $m\mu$, where the absorption of the reagent solution was comparatively small.

Effect of NaOH Concentration.—The maximum permissible concentration of the alkali was found to be 0.04 to 0.05 N in the total volume, beyond which the optical density diminished.

Beer's Law.—Curves I and II, Fig. 2 show the linear relationship between the metal concentration and optical density, measured 30-45 minutes after preparing the solutions.

FIG. 2

Beer's law curves.

Curve I	—Co-dimethylrubeanic acid;	395 $m\mu$.
Curve II	—Co-diethyl-	" " 395 $m\mu$.
Curve III	—Ni-dimethyl-	" " 480 $m\mu$.
Curve IV	—Ni-diethyl-	" " 490 $m\mu$.
Curve V	—Pd-dimethyl-	" " 395 $m\mu$.
Curve VI	—Pd-diethyl-	" " 395 $m\mu$.
Curve VII	—Ru-dimethyl (diethyl)	" " 625 $m\mu$.

Sensitivity: 0.00417 Co/cm² (Sandell) and 0.025 γ Co/cm² (practical) for the dimethyl derivative and 0.0043 γ Co/cm² (Sandell) and 0.03 γ Co/cm² (practical) for the diethylrubeanic acid.

Effect of Diverse Ions.—The following ions interfered as they either formed precipitates or coloured solution on the addition of the reagent: Fe^{3+} , Fe^{2+} , Bi^{3+} , Hg^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Ag^+ , Au^{3+} , Pt^{4+} , Pd^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , VO_3^- , etc. The use of potassium cyanide to mask the colour effect due to nickel may be made as in the case of rubeanic acid (cf. Part I, *loc. cit.*).

Procedure.—Sodium acetate (1 c.c.) and pyridine (5 c.c.) were added to an almost neutral solution of cobalt, containing less than 0.1 mg. Co. About 10-15 c.c. of water was added, followed by 2 c.c. of the reagent solution. The volume was made up to 25 c.c. with water and the optical density measured at 395 $m\mu$, after 30-45 minutes, against a suitable reagent blank.

Determination of Nickel

With very dilute nickel solutions in presence of pyridine, dimethylrubeanic acid developed a purple-yellow colour, and the diethyl derivative, a rose-red solution. With low concentrations of nickel, the colour development was retarded by excess of alkali in the case of diethylrubeanic acid. The colour systems obeyed Beer's law.

Standard nickel solution contained 2.5 γ Ni/c.c. Reagent solution comprised equal volumes of 0.2% alcoholic solution of dimethyl- or diethyl-rubeanic acid and $N/4$ aqueous NaOH solution.

Absorption Curves.—The absorption maximum for the purple-yellow colour of nickel dimethylrubeanic acid was found to lie at 485 $m\mu$ and that for the rose-red colour of nickel diethylrubeanic acid at 490 $m\mu$ (cf. Curves III and IV, Fig. 1). All optical density measurements were made against a reagent blank, which showed only a negligible absorption beyond the ultraviolet region.

Effect of NaOH Concentration.—It was observed that dilute alkali solutions (up to 10 c.c. of $N/4$) for 2 γ Ni/c.c. had no effect on the colour intensity of nickel dimethylrubeanate, when added after the reagent solution. But the addition of alkali to the diethyl system retarded the colour development. Thus, when 1 c.c. of $N/4$ -NaOH solution was added to a solution containing 2 p.p.m. Ni, 5 c.c. pyridine and 2 c.c. of the reagent solution in a total volume of 25 c.c., made up with water, the maximum colour intensity was reached only after 30 minutes. Under the same conditions, but with 2 c.c. of alkali, it took about 1½ hours, and with 10 c.c., about 3 hours for the complete colour development.

Beer's Law.—Both the systems followed Beer's law (cf. Curves III & IV, Fig. 2). When diethylrubeanic acid was used as the reagent, optical density measurements were taken after a lapse of 30 minutes from the time of preparing the solutions.

Stability of the Colour.—The purple-yellow colour of the nickel dimethylrubeanate developed within 15 minutes after the addition of the reagent, and was stable for about 3-5 hours. The optical density of the coloured system in the case of diethylrubeanic acid remained unchanged for about an hour, but increased slowly by 8-10% after 12 hours.

Sensitivity: 0.0075 γ Ni/cm² (S) and 0.03 γ Ni/cm² (P) for dimethylrubeanic acid. 0.008 γ Ni/cm² (S) and 0.03 γ Ni/cm² (P) for diethylrubeanic acid.

Effect of Diverse Ions: Same as under cobalt.

Procedure.—Pyridine (5 c.c.) and water (10 c.c.) were added to the sample solution, which was previously made almost neutral. The reagent solution (2 c.c., for dimethyl- and 1 c.c. for diethyl-rubeanic acid) was added and the volume made up to 25 c.c. with water. The optical density was measured against a reagent blank after 10 minutes for dimethyl- and after 30 minutes for diethyl-rubeanic acid.

Determination of Palladium

The yellow colour developed by the addition of dimethyl- or diethyl-rubeanic acid reagent solution (vide under Ni) to an aqueous pyridine solution of palladium gave decreasing values of absorption at higher wave-lengths (cf. Curves V & VI, Fig. 1). 395 $m\mu$ was found to be the most desirable wave-length, at which the reagent absorption was quite small. Addition of an excess of alkali was found to retard the colour formation. Thus, 1 c.c. of $N/4$ -NaOH, added 3-5 minutes after the reagent, diminished the optical density of a solution containing 2 p.p.m. Pd by about 5% when measured at 395 $m\mu$, after half an hour. The colour development was rather slow at higher concentrations (>4 p.p.m.) of palladium, taking about 20 to 30 minutes to reach the maximum intensity. But the intensity afterwards remained unchanged for more than 24 hours. The systems were found to obey Beer's law (cf. Curves V & VI, Fig. 2).

Sensitivity: 0.014 γ Pd/cm² (S) and 0.05 γ Pd/cm² (P) for dimethylrubeanic acid. 0.013 γ Pd/cm² (S) and 0.05 γ Pd/cm² (P) for diethylrubeanic acid.

Procedure.—Same as that for nickel. But 1 c.c. of the reagent solution was used, and the optical density was measured at 395 $m\mu$, about half an hour after preparing the solution.

Determination of Ruthenium

The procedure adopted was similar to that for rubeanic acid. Ruthenium solutions, when warmed with dimethyl- or diethylrubeanic acid in presence of HCl, developed a blue colour. The absorption maximum of this solution lay in the region of 600-640 $m\mu$ for dimethyl- and 610-660 $m\mu$ for diethyl-rubeanic acid (cf. Curve VII, Fig. 1). 625 $m\mu$ was chosen for the analytical work.

HCl-EtOH mixture (2.5 c.c., 1:1 by vol.) and 0.2% alcoholic reagent solution (1 c.c.) were sufficient to develop the maximum colour intensity. But when the ruthenium content was more than 5 p.p.m., an excess of the reagent as well as of the acid-alcohol mixture were necessary. Beer's law was found to hold good up to 4 p.p.m. Ru for dimethyl and up to 6 p.p.m. for the diethyl derivative (Curve VII, Fig. 2). Both the reagents gave the same sensitivity of 0.01 γ Ru/cm² (S) and 0.04 γ Ru/cm² (P).